

VULNERABILITIES OF WORKERS IN INFORMAL SECTOR: A STUDY OF WOMEN STREET VENDORS

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Abstract

Women's participation in labour market has drastically increased during the last two decades on a global level. The National Commission for Women estimates that 94 percent of the total female workforce is found in the unorganized sector. With the advent of industrialization, employment opportunities available to the women have assumed wider dimensions both in developed and developing countries. It has been increasingly realized that women along with men play a significant role in the context of prosperity of the country as well as for the purpose of raising standard of living. Women workers contribute significantly to national development by performing remunerated and unremunerated work. Women's contribution to the economy by and large remains unrecognized. Yet, their services are valuable.

Key Words: *labour market, unorganized sector, industrialization, self-employment, street vending, vulnerable.*

INTRODUCTION

Women street vendors in the city of Bengaluru are among the most deprived sections of the informal sector or self-employed worker segment. Their working condition is very depressing and miserable as they perpetually work in a state of uncertainty, facing an array of challenges. The process of purchasing daily-use commodities is no easy task with constant market fluctuations. Besides, middlemen dominate the wholesale markets. As most vendors deal in perishables, the goods have to be carefully selected, bought at reasonable rates and sold to customers at the right time. However, despite their poor working conditions they seem to exhibit remarkable entrepreneurial skills. This article examines the working conditions of women street vendors and their impact on an average vendor's quality of life. Further, the findings also highlight the reasons for choosing this job, the type of commodities they sell, the

mode of selling goods in a competitive environment, the risk factors involved in their business, the nature of illness they suffer during the course of their work, the issues related to civic amenities at the vending places, their earnings per month, and the working hours per day.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To analyse the vulnerabilities of women street vendors.

METHODOLOGY

The unit of analysis of the present study is the 'Women street vendors'. To analyse the key objectives of this paper exploratory and descriptive design has been adopted. Data was collected from secondary sources which composed of research articles published in journals, magazines, write-ups, gist of policy brief on women, NEWS papers, official documents were referred to determine the impact and provide policy suggestions.

VULNERABILITIES OF WOMEN STREET VENDORS

1. FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO STREET VENDING ACTIVITIES

Over the past few decades, there has been a steady increase in street vending activity by women. Several factors have contributed to women trading on the streets, despite the fact that this occupation comes with its own set of uncertainties, inadequate income, lack of basic facilities, harassment by law enforcers, and being perceived as illegal work. Poverty and lack of gainful employment in the rural areas and in the smaller towns have driven a large number of women to the cities for work and livelihood. Low barriers to entry, limited initial investment and flexible hours of work have attracted them to this occupation. Most of the women have taken into street vending mainly to supplement the spouse's earnings because they feel the increasing cost of living in a city such as Bengaluru, it is very difficult to sustain with a single income.

2. NATURE OF COMMODITIES SOLD

Street vendors in Bengaluru City sell a wide range of products such as clothes and hosiery, leather made items, plastic goods and various household necessities which are manufactured in small scale or home-based industries. Apart from non-agricultural products, they also sell vegetables and fruits. Thus the street vendors provide a market for both small scales as well as agricultural workers. They also support the urban rich by selling daily requirements right in their doorsteps. The study intends to know about the commodities sold by the sample respondents. It is noted that an overwhelming majority of the women reported trading perishable goods mainly fruits, vegetables and flowers. They also sell processed and cooked food and non-perishable items such as clothes, cosmetics, bangles, household articles,

puppets and dolls.

3. MODE AND PLACE OF SELLING GOODS

Street vendors have different modes of selling their goods. They could be either selling their wares from a regular, fixed spot or could be wandering through the roads with their pushcarts or baskets. The stationary vendors usually occupy space on the pavements or any public spots, whereas the mobile vendors move from place to place carrying their goods in push carts or baskets on their heads, or baskets attached to cycles. Some of them sell their wares in moving buses or trains. Majority of the women reported selling their wares in places such as the pavements/street corners of marketplaces. They are also found selling their goods from one area to another, either carrying their wares on push carts/bicycles or baskets placed over their heads. These type of women are found to be both in residential as well as commercial areas. Some of them are also seen near traffic signals.

4. COMPETITION AT WORK PLACE

With an increasing number of street vendors, competition among them has also risen proportionately. Competition for space in the streets and access to customers is aggressive in many cities. Also, surviving as a street vendor requires a certain amount of skill and experience. Vendors must be able to negotiate effectively with wholesalers and customers (WEIGO 2013). All the women face significant amount of competition and this affects their earnings, besides having to negotiate rising costs. Street vendors say that their products are more expensive, but they find it difficult to pass on the rising costs to consumers, who invariably expect lower prices and haggle for a good bargain. It is to be noted that more competition means vendors tend to take home fewer earnings. Moreover, supermarkets and malls in the organized sector sell their products at much cheaper prices than the vendors and also frequently offer discounts and freebies to attract customers which have led to a reduction in business for street vendors.

5. RISK FACTORS INVOLVED IN THE BUSINESS

Street vending addresses major social and economic problems in developing countries through the provision of employment opportunities to the urban poor. However, due to the informal and unstructured nature of this business, the activities of the practitioners are not regulated. This gives ample room for unlawful practices. As a result, the vendors face risk in their business. Lack of safety or security has been reported as a key issue, while women also face the problem of shortage of funds to start and run the business, insufficient demand, lack of family and Government support and lack of storage facilities is a risk factor.

6. NATURE OF HEALTH PROBLEMS

The informal and unstructured nature of this occupation is characterized by hazardous working conditions and heavy physical strain. Women street vendors, particularly, face different kinds of livelihood risks because of the legal, physical, and socio-cultural environment in which they work. Street vending is labour-intensive and involves intense physical strain which in turn makes women vendors generally tired and vulnerable to various health problems. In addition, high pollution levels in open public places can further aggravate the poor health conditions of street vendors. The present article highlights the nature of health problems faced by women street vendors. Women are found to be suffering from asthma, hyperacidity, malaria, rashes on their skin and skin allergies due to heavy exposure to sun's rays, urinary tract infection, anxiety and high blood pressure. Fever, fatigue, joint pain, headaches, stress and hypertension are some of the common issues found among women.

7. LACK OF BASIC FACILITIES AT WORK PLACE

The article shows that a substantial proportion of respondents do not have access to clean, drinking water facilities at their workplace. The street vendors should be supported by the state with basic civic amenities such as potable water, clean toilets, proper street lights, concrete pavements, parking lots and restrooms. Limited access to drinking water and clean toilets is one of the major problems faced due to which, the women vendors experience a lot of health problems. Majority of the women do not have access to toilet facilities at the workplace. The lack of clean toilets has an adverse effect on women's health and many suffer from urinary tract infections and kidney ailments.

Conclusion

Street vendors are an urban asset because they not only generate income and employment but also provide useful service to the community by providing door to door service of daily essentials. This article makes an in-depth analysis of the working conditions of the women street vendors. The present working conditions of the vendors are characterised by their daily struggle in managing their household responsibilities and work, the huge competition in their profession due to the incapacity of the formal sector to provide jobs and the exorbitant rate of interest charged by the private money lenders. A majority of the urban, informal sector workers live in and around slums, lack social protection and access to basic healthcare and welfare schemes. They live and work in unhealthy and unsafe environments. Street vendors have little or no social protection and their working conditions expose them to a variety of safety and health issues. The lack of recognition of the role of the street vendors culminates in a multitude

of problems faced by them namely obtaining license, insecurity of earnings, insecurity of place of hawking, gratifying officers and musclemen, constant eviction threat, fines and harassment by traffic.

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